

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KWAGBEDZI****FIRST NAME: LIZZY-ANN****PROGRAM CODE: DSSD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium.

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is %

The author used MSWord 2016 on Windows 11

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. How can plagiarism be avoided?

- Use different authors for different sources of information.
- Copy information for your work without acknowledging it.
- Paraphrase information taken from others.
- To properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using.¹**

2. Why is American English used as “World English?”

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1. Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 35.

It is because of American English's dominant influence.²

It is because of Americans' military power.

It is because of Americans' understanding of the English Language.

It is because American English is very easy to learn.

3. In what way is the research problem relevant to the overall dissertation?

It provides information for references.

It differentiates between a good thesis and a bad one.

It forms the foundation of the dissertation.³

It indicates the overall summary of the dissertation.

4. Relate feedback to the improvement of a dissertation.

Feedback helps highlight the weaknesses and strengths of a student's dissertation.⁴

Feedback helps only to highlight the power of a student's dissertation.

² Ibid., 25.

³ Turabian Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 28-30.

⁴ Ibid., 127-128.

- Feedback helps only highlight the shortcomings of a student's dissertation.
- Feedback can frustrate the confidence level of a student in dissertation writing.

5. How relevant is the citation to a doctoral student in dissertation writing?

- Readers will know how knowledgeable the student is in dissertation writing.
- It tells readers where the facts of the student came from.⁵**
- Citations do not show the importance of referencing a source of information.
- Citation can deceive the reader about information included in a dissertation.

6. Accuracy and facts are critical in writing a dissertation. How do they affect the trust of readers?

- It makes readers accept the writer's argument to be true.⁶**

⁵ Ibid., 139-146.

⁶ Ibid., 139-140.

- It reduces the confidence level readers have in research.
- Readers may see themselves to be unfairly treated.
- It affects readers' reliability of the study.

7. What role does the research design play in the research process?

- It ensures a well-stated problem.
- Provides information on the population of a study.
- It provides a plan for the researcher to answer the research question and achieve the stated objectives.⁷**
- Creates avenues for the proper sample to be selected for a research study.

8. What is sampling?

- The process of differentiating between quantitative variables and qualitative variables.
- The process of randomly selecting participants for a study.
- The process of analyzing participants' data.
- The process of selecting participants for a study.⁸**

⁷ James, Jr. Sampson P., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research. Second Edition* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 35.

⁸ Ibid., 46.

9. How important is the discussion of findings to a dissertation?

- It shows how the researcher properly integrates the literature into the discussion.⁹**
- It shows the knowledge base of the researcher in writing a dissertation.
- It enables researchers to present their views on the findings.
- It shows that a researcher can pick the views of any writer to support his or her findings.

10. How should foreign words and phrases be used in English text?

- They should be put in quotations.
- They should be capitalized.
- They should be italicized and have the appropriate accents.¹⁰**
- They should be translated into English before use.

⁹ Ibid., 56-59.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th Edition (European Commission, 2021), 48-49.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenwerck, Laurent and Kabiru, Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed., 2021.

James, P. Sampson, Jr. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Sta. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.